

A study on the mononuclear bivalent manganese and copper complexes of twelve membered hexaaza [N₆] macrocyclic ligand : Synthesis, spectral and *in vitro* antifungal screening

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Abstract : New manganese(II) and copper(II) complexes of 12-membered macrocyclic Schiff base ligand containing thiosemicarbazone moiety have been prepared having general composition [MLX₂] where M = Mn^{II} or Cu^{II}, L = 3,4,9,10-tetra-2-furanyl-1,2,5,6,8,11-hexaazacyclododeca-7,12-dithione-2,4,8,10-tetraene and X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and NCS⁻. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility measurements and spectral (IR, electronic, EPR and mass) techniques. The IR spectra of complexes suggested that ligand is coordinated to the metal ion through imine nitrogen atoms. On the basis of spectral studies, an octahedral and tetragonal geometry has been assigned for Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively. EPR spectra of polycrystalline Mn^{II} complexes gave an isotropic signal with *g* value centered around free electron *g* value. EPR spectra of Mn^{II} complexes in DMSO showed hyperfine splitting containing six lines whereas EPR spectra of polycrystalline Cu^{II} complexes showed anisotropic signal. Conductivity measurements supported the non electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic moment data suggested the paramagnetic and high spin nature of the complexes. All the complexes have also been tested *in vitro* against a number of pathogenic fungi. Results indicated that the complexes exhibited good antifungal activity. Thermal analysis of reported complexes suggested no weight loss up to 120–150 °C and indicated the absence of water molecule either in or outside the coordination sphere.

Keywords : Spectroscopic, macrocyclic, octahedral, antifungal, tetragonal, anisotropic.

Introduction

Metal complexes with macrocyclic ligands have gained great research interest in recent years¹. The importance of macrocyclic complexes in coordination chemistry is because of various applications in biological processes such as photosynthesis and dioxygen transport². Schiff base macrocyclic ligands derived from thiosemicarbazones are of significant interest not only for their wide biological properties as antibacterial, anticancer, antiviral, and antifungal agents^{3,4} but also for their capacity for chemical recognition of anions and metals of biochemical and environmental importance⁵⁻⁷. Macrocyclic complexes attract attention of chemist because of their resemblance with many natural systems like porphyrins and cobalamines⁸. The activity of such compounds is strongly

dependent upon the nature of the heteroatomic ring and position of attachment to the ring as well as the form of the thiosemicarbazone moiety⁹⁻¹¹. In the light of above facts the present study deals with the synthesis, spectroscopic, thermal and antifungal evaluation of manganese(II), copper(II) complexes, synthesized from 3,4,9,10-tetra-2-furanyl-1,2,5,6,8,11-hexaazacyclododeca-7,12-dithione-2,4,8,10-tetraene.

Experimental

All the starting chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and were of reagent grade.

Instrumentation :

The C and H were analyzed on Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. The nitrogen content of the complexes

was determined using Kjeldahl method. Molar conductance was measured on the ELICO (CM82T) conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature on Gouy balance using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-240 spectrophotometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were recorded on E_4 -EPR spectrometer using the OPPH as the g marker. EIMS mass spectra were recorded on Jeol, JMS-DX-303 mass spectrometer. Thermal analysis of complexes was carried out TGA-DTA Shimadzu-50 thermo analyzer.

General procedure for synthesis of complexes :

A template reaction was carried out to synthesize the complexes. An EtOH solution (20 ml) of the respective divalent metal salt (10 mmol) was mixed with a hot EtOH solution (20 ml) of thiosemicarbazide (20 mmol). Then an EtOH solution (20 ml) of furil (20 mmol) in the presence of a few drops of conc. HCl was added to the resultant solution. The solution was refluxed for about 5–7 h. The coloured complexes precipitated out on cooling the reaction solution overnight. The complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over P_4O_{10} . Purity of complexes was checked by TLC. The general reaction for the formation of complexes is given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

The general composition for the complexes was found MLX_2 (where $M = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{NO}_3^-, \text{NCS}^-$). All the complexes provide proper C, H and N

results (Table 1). The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMSO and DMF.

Molar conductance measurements :

The low values of molar conductance ($12\text{--}18 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) carried out in DMF at the concentration of $10^{-3} M$, indicated (Table 1) the non-electrolytic nature of complexes¹². The low value suggested the presence of anions inside the coordination sphere and bonded to the metal ion. Therefore, these complexes may be formulated as $[\text{MLX}_2]$. The low value of molar conductance may be due to large size of anionic coordination sphere¹³.

Magnetic moment measurements :

Magnetic moment measurements for the complexes have been made at room temperature. The manganese(II) complexes showed magnetic moment in the range 5.91–5.95 B.M. (Table 2), close to the spin only value (5.92 B.M.) a value in accordance with a high spin configuration indicated the presence of octahedral¹⁴ environment around the manganese(II) ion in the complexes whereas the copper(II) complexes showed magnetic moment in the range 1.96–1.98 B.M., corresponding to one electron. It was slightly higher than those expected for a d^9 system. This may be attributed to the incomplete quenching of the orbital contribution to the magnetic moment or to spin orbit coupling¹⁵.

IR spectra :

The relevant IR spectral bands of complexes are listed in Table 3. The IR spectra of the complexes showed the absence of absorption *ca.* 3400 cm^{-1} indicated the ab-

Table 1. Physical properties and analytical data of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes

Complexes	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%):			
					Found (Calcd.)			
					M	C	H	N
[MnLCl ₂]	Pale yellow	248	12	62	9.02	42.82	2.19	13.64
MnC ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂					(8.92)	(42.85)	(2.27)	(13.63)
[MnL(NO ₃) ₂]	Light yellow	260	15	65	8.92	39.15	2.19	16.76
MnC ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₁₀ S ₂					(8.22)	(39.46)	(2.09)	(16.74)
[MnL(NCS) ₂]	Off white	256	18	68	8.52	43.25	2.19	16.72
MnC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₄ S ₄					(8.30)	(43.57)	(2.11)	(16.94)
[CuLCl ₂]	Light blue	252	15	64	9.98	42.75	2.15	13.64
CuC ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂					(10.09)	(42.30)	(2.24)	(13.46)
[CuL(NO ₃) ₂]	Light green	245	14	60	8.99	39.05	2.15	16.78
CuC ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₁₀ S ₂					(9.30)	(38.99)	(2.06)	(16.54)
[CuL(NCS) ₂]	Green	255	12	64	8.96	43.45	2.17	16.95
CuC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₄ S ₄					(9.41)	(43.04)	(2.09)	(16.74)

Table 2. Electronic, EPR spectral and magnetic moment data of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes

Complexes	ν_1 (cm^{-1})	ν_2 (cm^{-1})	ν_3 (cm^{-1})	ν_4 (cm^{-1})	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	G
[MnLCl ₂]	19950	23204	29883	31650	5.91	-	-	-
[MnL(NO ₃) ₂]	19680	23980	28680	31530	5.95	-	-	-
[MnL(NCS) ₂]	19760	24915	28860	31740	5.93	-	-	-
[CuLCl ₂]	14650	25560	-	-	1.96	2.15	2.07	2.14
[CuL(NO ₃) ₂]	15384	-	-	-	1.98	2.27	2.14	1.92
[CuL(NCS) ₂]	14870	24940	-	-	1.95	2.24	2.13	1.84

Table 3. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes

Complexes	$\nu(\text{NH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
[MnLCl ₂]	3216 b	1565 s	827 m	420 m
[MnL(NO ₃) ₂]	3220 b	1550 s	820 m	425 m
[MnL(NCS) ₂]	3220 b	1545 s	825 m	410 m
[CuLCl ₂]	3220 b	1562 s	827 m	445 m
[CuL(NO ₃) ₂]	3218 b	1560 s	822 m	430 m
[CuL(NCS) ₂]	3220 b	1558 s	820 m	450 m

sence of free amino group. A medium intensity band at *ca.* 1580–1620 cm^{-1} characteristic to the imine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ¹⁶ stretching frequency appearing at lower frequency, suggested that metal is coordinated to ligand through the azomethine nitrogen atoms. The appearance of a band at *ca.* 410–450 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ also indicated that metal-ligand coordination takes place through imine nitrogen atoms. The band assigned to thioamide $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ ¹⁷ at *ca.* 825 cm^{-1} appeared in the spectrum of free thiosemicarbazide remains almost at the same position in the complexes. It indicated that thioamide sulphur did not involve in coor-

dination. Thus, it may be concluded that ligand acted in tetradentate fashion and coordinated to metal ions through imine nitrogen atoms.

Bands due to anions :

The IR spectral bands at *ca.* 1450–1400, 1320–1290 and 1070–1020 cm^{-1} , in the spectra of nitrate complexes suggested that both nitrate groups are coordinated to the central metal ion in unidentate fashion¹⁸. Thiocyanate anion may coordinate in different ways. It can show linkage isomerism. The complexes under study showed a single sharp band at *ca.* 2050–2080 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1) indicated that both thiocyanate groups are coordinated to metal through N atom¹⁹.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of reported complexes were recorded in DMSO. The Mn^{II} complexes showed weak electronic spectral bands in the range 19680–19950, 23204–24915, 28680–29883 and 31650–31740 cm^{-1}

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of [CuL(NCS)₂].

(Table 2). These bands may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4D)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4P)$ transitions respectively. The positions of bands indicated that Mn^{II} complexes have an overall octahedral geometry²⁰. The electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes (Fig. 2) displayed one broad absorption band in the range 14650–15384 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) and in some complexes a well defined shoulder at 25450–25560 cm⁻¹. These spectral bands may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g} (d_{x^2-y^2} - d_{z^2} \nu_1)$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g} (d_{x^2-y^2} - d_{zy} \nu_2)$ transitions indicating a tetragonal environment around Cu^{II} ion²¹ in the complexes.

Fig. 2. Electronic spectrum of [CuL(NO₃)₂].

EPR spectra :

EPR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes were recorded at room temperature in the polycrystalline state, on X band at frequency of 9.1 GHz under the magnetic field strength of 3100G. The present Cu^{II} complexes exhibited well resolved anisotropic signals (Fig. 3) in the parallel and perpendicular regions. The observed data showed that g_{\parallel}

Fig. 3. The X band EPR spectrum of [CuLCl₂].

= 2.15–2.27 and $g_{\perp} = 2.07$ –2.14. The g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values was found around 2 and $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ suggested major distortion from O_h symmetry in the Cu^{II} complexes²². Kivelson and Neiman²³ have shown that g_{\parallel} is a moderately sensitive function for indicating covalency. Relatively speaking $g_{\parallel} > 2.3$ is characteristic of anionic environment and $g_{\parallel} < 2.3$ of a covalent environment in M–L bonding. The observed g_{\parallel} values were found less than 2.3 and were in agreement with the covalent character of the M–L bond. The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0023$ observed for the complexes indicated that unpaired electron is localized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of Cu^{II} ion. Thus, a tetragonal geometry is proposed for the aforesaid complexes. $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$, which is the measure of exchange interaction between the metal centers in a polycrystalline solid, has been calculated. According to Hathaway²⁴ if $G > 4$, the exchange interaction is negligible and $G < 4$ indicates considerable exchange interaction in the solid complexes. The reported complexes showed G values are < 4 indicating the exchange interaction in complexes. EPR spectra of Mn^{II} complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample and in DMSO solution as well. EPR spectra of polycrystalline samples gave one broad isotropic signal centered on the approximate free electron g value (2.0023). In DMSO solution, the complexes gave EPR spectra containing six lines (Fig. 4) arising due to hyperfine interaction²⁵ between the unpaired electrons with the Mn nucleus ($I = 5/2$).

EIMS mass spectra :

The electronic impact mass spectrum of the Mn^{II} chloro complex showed a molecular ion $[MnC_{22}H_{14}N_6O_4S_2Cl_2]^+$

Fig. 4. The X band EPR spectrum of [MnLCl₂].

Fig. 5. Antifungal screening data of the complexes : (■) *A. niger*, (□) *F. odum*, (▨) *A. alternata*, (▤) *F. oxysporum*.

peak at *m/z* 616 amu and Cu^{II} nitrate complex showed molecular ion [CuC₂₂H₁₄N₈O₄S₂]⁺ peak at *m/z* 678 amu. The calculated mass of the Cu^{II} nitrate complex was 677 amu, therefore the molecular ion peak may be corresponding to isotopic (M⁺ + 1) peak. The observed data suggested the monomeric nature of the complexes and confirmed the proposed formulae.

Antifungal screening :

The antifungal activity of reported macrocyclic complexes was tested against various fungi viz. *A. niger*, *A. alternata*, *F. oxysporum* and *F. odum* under laboratory conditions by food poison technique²⁶ at 50–100 ppm concentrations. The experimental data (Table 4) suggested that complexes provided satisfactory antifungal properties. % inhibition was calculated by using the formula²⁷, %I = 100 (C - T)/C, where C and T are the diameter (mm) of the fungus colony in the control and treatment respectively.

Table 4. Antifungal screening data of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes

Complexes	Fungal inhibition % (conc. in ppm)							
	<i>A. niger</i>		<i>A. alternata</i>		<i>F. oxysporum</i>		<i>F. odum</i>	
[MnLCl ₂]	50	100	50	100	50	100	50	100
[MnL(NO ₃) ₂]	45	55	45	58	47	60	42	48
[MnL(NCS) ₂]	47	55	46	56	49	53	48	58
[CuLCl ₂]	42	50	44	58	47	51	46	55
[CuL(NO ₃) ₂]	48	58	49	55	48	58	45	57
[CuL(NCS) ₂]	45	60	45	60	45	55	47	62
[CuL(NCS) ₂]	48	55	47	60	46	58	49	60

Thermal analysis :

Thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis of some reported complexes were carried out in the

temperature range 50–700 °C. The TG curves of complexes clearly indicated the absence of water molecules inside or outside the coordination sphere as no significant mass loss observed up to 120–150 °C. The decomposition of organic part of the complexes started around 250 °C as indicated by major fall in the % weight loss. Finally, complexes converted into their metal oxides as end product around 650 °C. The conversion of complexes into metal oxide has been found in accordance with the proposed formulae for the complexes. In DTA curve of Mn^{II} chloro complex, three exothermic peaks have been observed in the temperature range 250–540 °C. The TGA curve of Cu^{II} nitrate complex showed that the decomposition started nearly at 390 °C. The general pattern of thermal degradation of the complexes may be given as follows :

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